

A NOTE ON THE HYDROGEN-ION CONCENTRATION AND ABSORPTION OF NICKEL ACETYLACETONE

BY S. C. TRIPATHI AND SATYA PRAKASH

It was observed that the divalent nickel formed a complex with the enolic form of acetylacetoné. McKenzie *et al.* (*J. Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 1944, 78, 70) using the magnetic-criterion for indicating covalent bonding of Ni, found that the ionic chelate had absorption spectra similar to those of chelating agents, but that the absorption spectra for the covalently bonded chelates contained strong absorption bands characteristic of the chelate and hence, of the metal donor bond.

In the present note, our results on potentiometric and colorimetric titrations of the nickel chelates at various concentrations are recorded.

To a known volume of nickel nitrate solution (0.1508M), different concentrations of acetylacetoné were added. The mixtures were allowed to stand for a few hours to attain equilibrium. To a known volume of this mixture were added varying con-

FIG. 1

Alkali (NaOH in c.c.).

Curves I-III refer respectively to 0.1538 M Ni with (1) 0.4M, (2) 0.5M, (3) 0.6M acetyl acetone against alkali. Curves IV and V refer respectively to 0.1538 M-Ni and 0.5M acetyl acetone against alkali.

centrations of standard caustic soda solution, keeping the total volume constant. These sets were left over for nearly 24 hours and they were studied for their absorption and H^+ -ion concentration. The results are graphically represented in Figs 1 and 2.

It will be seen from the graph of the potentiometric titration that as the concentration of caustic soda is increased, there is a steady rise in the pH up to 8.0 (Fig. 1).

FIG. 2

Curves I-III refer respectively to 0.1-53 M Ni + (1) 0.4, (2) 0.5, (3) 0.6mM acetyl acetone against pH and curve IV to 0.1538 M -Ni against pH .

The results of absorption indicate that at about pH 8.25, the complex formation is complete, and therefore subsequent addition of caustic soda does not show any further increase in absorption. At about pH 12 the complex breaks and precipitation occurs and the absorption again rapidly falls.